

STUDIES ON GLASS COMPOSITIONS. A PRELIMINARY NOTE

By P. SEN

The use of talc as a glass making material in place of sand and lime has been studied.

The effect of magnesia as a glassy constituent has been studied by Turner and his co-workers (*J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1919, 3, 275); they found the effect to be beneficial in imparting the properties of chemical durability and lamp-working in preference to lime; but it imparts higher viscosity than lime.

Kühl (*Glashuete*, 1927, 57, 123; *Pottery Gaz.*, 1928, 53, 611) used German dolomite and found that when 4-5% of magnesia was substituted for lime, the resistance of this glass against abrupt changes in temperature was increased. Besborodov (*Keram. Rund*, 1928, 36, 365) found that substitution up to a maximum of 5.78% of magnesia for lime increased the resistance to sodium carbonate solution and decreased the resistance to hydrochloric acid solution.

With the increasing amount of magnesia, the viscosity, surface tension and difficulty of melting are increased. But Kühl (*Glashuete*, 1933, 63, 371) found that even with the use of magnesia in the form of dolomite, the melting was considerably facilitated when alkalies and lime were simultaneously replaced by barium oxide. The quality of the glass was also improved considerably as it gave increased density, refractive index, hardness and modulus of rupture. This, therefore, gives the clue as to the feasibility of preparing magnesia glasses with proper working properties by substituting lime wholly by some other glass forming oxide. With the advent of the machine operation glasses were required with larger working range and freedom from de-vitrification. Addition of alumina as felspar accomplished these purposes (Ferguson, *Ceram. Ind.*, 1934, 22, 362). There is a general agreement that alumina in glass promotes resistance to thermal and mechanical shocks, imparts lower annealing temperature, and stability against de-vitrification.

All previous workers working with dolomite were faced with the formation of seedy glass and difficulty in firing. Parmelee and Silverman (*Glass Ind.*, 1936, 17, 111) found that addition of alumina decreased the melting rate and the effect decreased with the rising temperature. The total elimination of lime and introduction of alumina generally give rise to $\text{MgO-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$, the system which has been studied by Rankin and Merwin (*Amer. J. Sci.*, 1918, 45, 301). This system has binary compounds $2\text{MgO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$, $\text{MgO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$, $\text{MgO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ and a ternary compound $2\text{MgO} \cdot 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{SiO}_2$, all with lower melting points than MgO itself. The refractory character of the individual

oxides and of most of the binary compounds and binary mixtures is no longer evident. The lowest point on the *liquidus* is the eutectic at 1345°.

The present work is intended to find out compositions of industrially possible magnesia glass along with felspar which will help working properties. A new source of magnesia was tried, namely Talc. India possesses good deposits of talc and felspar and the work intended may open up a new line in the industrial glass manufacture.

EXPERIMENTAL

The raw materials used were I. C. I. heavy soda ash, finely ground Indian felspar and talc with the following composition :

TABLE I

	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Alkalis	Na ₂ CO ₃	Loss	NaCl & Na ₂ SO ₄
Felspar	63.83	21.11	0.08	0.21	0.07	13.25	...	0.28	...
Talc	62.1	2.3		2.1	30.3	...	...	3.10	...
Soda ash (I.C.I.)	...	...	...	Trace	Trace	...	96.6	3.10	Trace

Total batch of 100 g. of raw materials was weighed out, mixed in a mortar, shaken thoroughly in a glass jar for about five minutes for thorough mixing and then transferred to a quarter-pound fireclay crucible. The crucibles were placed in an oil-fired furnace and the temperature of melting for each case was observed by means of a Cambridge optical pyrometer and the time for melting noted. The range of compositions taken were: soda ash, 5-25; felspar, 25-75; and talc 10-50 parts by weight with a difference of 5 parts in each case as given in Table II. A rough idea of viscosity of each melt was obtained by drawing rods and by observing the ease of flow of the melt from the crucible.

TABLE II

Series	Melt No.	Soda ash	Felspar	Talc	Melting temp. & time.	Observations.
A	1	25	65	10	1320° & 4 hours.	Clear melt, light brownish amber colour with no seeds. Highly viscous.
"	2	"	60	15	"	Clear melt, greenish white colour at the centre of the melt. Very viscous.
"	3	"	55	20	"	Clear melt, greenish white in colour with a brownish tinge. No seeds, wires could be drawn. Viscosity lower than Nos. 1 & 2.

TABLE II (contd.)

Series.	Melt No.	Soda ash.	Felspar.	Talc.	Melting temp & time.	Observations.
A	4	25	50	25	1320° & 4 hours	Clear greenish white melt; very viscous.
"	5	"	45	30	"	Do.
"	6	"	40	35	"	Do.
"	7	"	35	40	"	Do. Less viscous than Nos. 1-6.
"	8	"	30	45	"	Do. Flowed out of the crucible readily.
"	9	"	25	50	"	Do. Least viscosity in series A.
B	10	20	70	10	"	Clear melt, amber colour with big bubbles. Very difficult to pour out; highly viscous.
"	11	"	65	15	"	Do. Bubble diameter less than No. 10.
"	12	"	60	20	"	Clear melt, greenish white in colour with seeds. Do.
"	13	"	55	25	"	Clear bright melt with seeds. Bubble diameter & viscosity lesser than No. 12.
"	14	"	50	30	"	Clear greenish white melt. Strips and not wires could be drawn. Highly viscous.
"	15	"	45	35	"	Do. Viscosity lower than No. 14.
"	16	"	40	40	"	Do.
"	17	"	35	45	"	Do. Flowed on tilting the crucible. Fluidity more than No. 16, nearly equal to No. 8.
"	18	"	30	50	"	Do. Fluidity more than No. 17. Viscosity is nearly equal to Nos. 6 & 7 of series A.
C	19	15	75	10	"	Light green, semi-melted mass.
"	21	"	65	20	"	Not very clear melt but more clear than No. 19.
"	23	"	55	30	"	Clear greenish white melt with seeds.
"	24	"	50	35	"	Clear melt with greenish smoky in colour.
"	25	"	45	40	"	Clear brownish melt. could not be poured out; viscosity more than series B.
"	28	"	40	45	"	Do.

TABLE II (*contd.*)

Series	Melt No.	Soda ash.	Felspar.	Talc.	Melting temp & time.	Observations
O	27	15	35	50	1320° & 4 hours	Clear greenish melt, transparency of the glass is more than No. 26. Viscosity more than series B, and practically could not be poured out.
D	28	10	75	15	1400° & 8 hours	Dirty glass
.	30	"	65	25	"	Clear green glass. Could not be poured out of the crucible; very viscous.
.	32	"	55	35	"	Clear fine melt, greenish in colour. Wire formed with difficulty. Viscosity lesser than No. 30.
"	33	"	50	40	1385° & 4 hours	Do (with seeds).
.	34	"	45	45	"	Do. Seeds lesser than No. 33. Wires could be drawn; viscosity lesser than No. 33.
	35	"	40	50	"	Most clear and transparent melt among series D (Nos. 28-35). Could be poured out of the crucible with difficulty. Seems to be more viscous than series A, B & C.
E	36	5	75	20	1400° & 8 hours	Did not form clear melt.
"	38	"	65	30	"	Do. More clear than No 36.
"	40	"	55	40	"	Clear, greenish white melt. Difficult to flow. Melt full of bubbles.
"	41	"	50	45	"	Melt full of big bubbles.
"	42	"	45	50	"	Clear transparent melt, greenish white in colour. Practically could not be poured out of the crucible. Highest viscosity amongst series A, B, C, D & E.

DISCUSSION

From the foregoing observations it is evident that

(i) With 5 parts of soda-ash and corresponding parts of felspar and talc, it is impossible to have a workable glass as per melt Nos. 36, 38, 40 and 41.

With 5 parts of soda ash, 45 of felspar and 50 parts of talc (No. 42) a clear glass is obtained, but due to its high viscosity it is not at all a workable glass. Moreover, they require highest temperature amongst all the glasses formed in the different series.

(ii) With 10 parts of soda ash and with corresponding parts of felspar and talc, clear glasses are obtained except No 28, but the viscosity of the glasses is very high amongst most of the melts.

(iii) With 15 to 25 parts of soda ash and with corresponding parts of felspar and talc, the melts form clear glasses except No 19. As the amount of soda ash decreases below 15, the chance of forming clear glassy melt is decreased.

Hence the workable range of the melts lies between 15 and 20 parts of soda ash. ⁵

(iv) Although clear glasses are obtained with felspar ranging from 25 to 75 parts, yet low viscosity melts are only with 25 to 35 parts of felspar.

(v) Talc has a higher fluxing action than felspar and imparts lower viscosity than felspar. In the case of talc, compositions with 10 to 50 parts of talc have melted into clear glasses but those with a higher felspar content are not workable

Substitution of talc for felspar, keeping soda ash constant, gives a more clear and less viscous glass.

C O N C L U S I O N

The four glasses, Nos. 8, 9, 17 and 18, may be industrially possible glasses which melted between 1320° to 1365°C, and have least viscosity amongst the series A, B, C, D and E. These glasses may be utilised for chemical and various other purposes.

Further investigation on the possibilities and properties of these glasses are in progress.

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